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Rules for the compilation of the catalogue, in British Museum. Department of Printed Books, *Catalogue of printed books in the British Museum*. London: The Trustees, 1841, p. v-ix. La riproduzione digitale è del progetto Google libri su una copia della University of Minnesota.

RULES

FOR THE COMPILATION OF THE CATALOGUE.

I. TITLES to be written on slips, uniform in size.

The entries of works in the collection of George the Third presented by George the Fourth to the Nation to be distinguished by a crown.

II. Titles to be arranged alphabetically, according to the English alphabet only (whatever be the order of the alphabet in which a foreign name might have to be entered in its original language) under the surname of the author, whenever it appears printed in the title, or in any other part of the book. If the name be supplied in MS. the work must nevertheless be considered anonymous or pseudonymous, as the case may be, and the MS. addition deemed merely a suggestion to which the librarian will attach such importance as he may think proper, on his own responsibility, in supplying the author's name between brackets, as hereafter directed.

In the alphabetical arrangement, initial prepositions, letters or articles to be taken in connection with the rest of the name.

III. If more than one name occur in the title, by which it may appear that the work is the production of more than one person, the first to be taken as the leading name.

IV. The works of sovereigns, or of princes of sovereign houses, to be entered under their Christian or first name, in their *English form*.

V. Works of Jewish Rabbis, as well as works of Oriental writers in general, to be entered under their first name.

VI. Works of friars, who, by the constitution of their order, drop their surname, to be entered under the Christian name; the name of the family, if ascertained, to be added in brackets. The same to be done for persons canonized as well as for those known under their first name only, to which, for the sake of distinction, they add that of their native place, or profession, or rank. Patronymics, or denominations, derived from the ancestors or names of other persons, to be used as surnames.

VII. The respondent or defender in a thesis to be considered its author, except when it unequivocally appears to be the work of the Præses.

VIII. When an author uses a Christian or first name only (either real or assumed), such name to be taken as a heading; and if more than one be used, the first to be preferred for the principal entry. The surname or family name, when known, to be added in brackets after the first name.

IX. Any act, resolution, or other document purporting to be agreed upon, authorized, or issued by assemblies, boards, or corporate bodies, (with the exception of academies, universities, learned societies, and religious orders, respecting which special rules are to be followed,) to be entered in distinct alphabetical series, under the name of the country or place from which they derive their denomination, or, for want of such denomination, under the name of the place whence their acts are issued.

X. Names of persons that may have been altered by

being used in various languages, to be entered under their vernacular form, if any instance occur of such persons having used it in any of their printed publications. With respect to places, the English form to be preferred.

XI. Works of authors who change their name or add to it a second, after having begun to publish under the first, to be entered under the first name, noticing any alteration which may have subsequently taken place.

XII. Foreign names, excepting French, preceded by a preposition, an article, or by both, to be entered under the letter immediately following. French names preceded by a preposition only, to follow the same rule; those preceded by an article, or by a preposition and an article, to be entered under the initial letter of the article. English surnames, of foreign origin, to be entered under their initial, even if originally belonging to a preposition. Foreign compound surnames to be entered under the initial of the first of them. In compound Dutch and English surnames the last name to be preferred, if no entry of a work by the same person occur in the catalogue under the first name only.

XIII. German names, in which the letters *ä, ö* or *ü* occur, to be spelt with the diphthong *ae, oe* and *ue* respectively.

XIV. Surnames of noblemen, though not expressed in the book, to be ascertained and written out as the heading of the entry. A person who has assumed titles not generally acknowledged, to have the words "calling himself," between brackets, to precede the assumed title.

XV. The same rule to be followed with respect to archbishops and bishops.

XVI. Christian names, included in parentheses, to follow the surname, and all to be written out in full, as far as they are known. In case of doubt on this or any other point, when the librarian is directed to supply any information in cataloguing, a note of interrogation to follow in such a position as to indicate clearly the point on which any doubt is entertained.

XVII. An author's rank in society, in cases in which he enjoyed any eminent honorary distinction, or office for life, not lower than that of knight, admiral, or general, to be stated in italics. Younger sons of dukes and marquesses, and all daughters of dukes, marquesses and earls, when not enjoying a distinct title, to have the designation *Lord* or *Lady* prefixed to the Christian name. All other younger branches of the nobility to have the word *Hon.* prefixed. The words *Right Hon.*, in the same situation, to distinguish privy councillors. Knights to be indicated merely by the appellation *Sir* prefixed to their first name. Titles of inferior rank, whether ecclesiastical, military, or civil, to be given only when necessary to make a distinction between authors having the same surname and Christian name.

Proper names commencing with Mc. or M' to be entered under Mac, with cross-references from the other forms.

Where a person is referred to in a title-page by a description sufficiently clear to render his or her iden-

tity obvious, the proper name of such person to be adopted as a heading, whether the work be historical or otherwise.

XVIII. The title of the book next to be written, and that expressed in as few words, and those only of the author, as may be necessary to exhibit to the reader all that the author meant to convey in the titular description of his work; the original orthography to be preserved. The number of the edition to be stated when appearing in the title.

In cataloguing sermons, the text always to be specified. The date at which preached to be inserted when it differs from that of publication.

XIX. Any striking imperfection in a book to be carefully noted; and any remarkable peculiarity, such as that of containing cancelled or duplicate leaves, &c. to be stated.

XX. When the book is without a title-page, its contents to be concisely, but sufficiently, stated in the words of the head-title, preceded by the word *begin*, (*beginning*) in italics; if there be no head-title, in those of the colophon, preceded by the word *end*, (*ending*); and when the want of title is owing to an imperfection, the words taken from either head-title or colophon to be included between parentheses. If both head-title and colophon be wanting or insufficient, then some idea of the work to be briefly given in English, between brackets, and the edition so accurately described as to be easily identified without fear of mistake.

XXI. Whenever one or more separate works are mentioned in the title of any publication, as forming part of it, the same to be particularly noticed in cataloguing the principal publication; and, if not mentioned in the title-page, this information to be added to the title between brackets or parentheses, as the case may be.

XXII. All works in Oriental characters or languages, except Hebrew, to be separately catalogued in a supplementary volume, according to special rules to be framed. The Bible and its parts, however, in whatever language or characters, to be entered in the general catalogue as hereafter directed.

XXIII. Works in more languages than one, accompanied by the original, to be entered in the original only, unless the title be accompanied by a translation or translations, in which case such translation also to be given. If no original text occur, the first language used in the title to be preferred. In all cases the several languages used in the book to be indicated at the end of the title, in italics.

XXIV. Works with a title in a language different from that used in the body of the book to be entered according to the above rule, merely stating at the end of the title in italics in what language the work is written.

XXV. The number of parts, volumes, fasciculi, or whatever may be the peculiar divisions of each author's work, to be next specified, in the words of the title.

XXVI. When nothing is said in the title respecting this point, if a work be divided into several portions, but the same pagination continue, or, when the pages are not numbered, if the same register continue, the work to be considered as divided into parts; if the progressive number of the pages or the register be interrupted, then each series of pages or letters of the register to be designated as a volume.

XXVII. Then the place where the book was printed; and in particular cases, as in the instance of early or very eminent typographers, the printer's name to be

specified. Next the date: when no date or place is specified, then either or both to be given, if known to, or conjectured by, the librarian; but in these instances to be included in brackets. The form to follow, whether fol., 4to, 8vo, &c.

XXVIII. If an early printed book, and in Gothic or black letter, the circumstance to be mentioned at the end of the title, thus:—G. L. or B. L.

XXIX. If printed on vellum, satin, on large or fine paper, or if an editio princeps of a classical or very distinguished writer, who flourished before 1700, or if privately printed, or a fac-simile or reprint of an early edition; if only a small number of copies were struck off, or if there be any manuscript notes, these peculiarities to be stated.

XXX. If the author of the manuscript notes be known, this information to be added between brackets. If the volume belonged to some very distinguished personage, the fact to be recorded in few words at the end of the entry, also between brackets.

XXXI. An editio princeps to be designed by the words *ED. PR.*, in italic capitals, at the end of the title. Manuscript notes to be indicated in italics at the end of the title, previous to the size of the volume, as follows:—*MS. NOTES.* If the notes be remarkably few, or the reverse, the circumstance to be noticed by prefixing to the above the word *FEW* or *COPIOUS*. Works printed *ON VELLUM* to be distinguished by these words, in small italic capitals, at the end of the title. The letters *L.P.* or *F.P.* in the same situation, to indicate copies on large or fine paper.

XXXII. Works published under initials, to be entered under the last of them; and should the librarian be able to fill up the blanks left, or complete the words which such initials are intended to represent, this to be done in the body of the title, and all the supplied parts to be included between brackets.

The rules applicable to proper names to be extended to initials.

XXXIII. When the author's name does not appear on the title or any other part of the work, the following rules to be observed. Anonymous publications relating to any act, or to the life of a person whose name occurs on the title of a work, to be catalogued under the name of such person. The same rule to be followed with respect to anonymous publications addressed (not merely dedicated) to any individual whose name occurs on the title.

XXXIV. When no such name of a person appears, then that of any assembly, corporate body, society, board, party, sect, or denomination appearing on the title to be preferred, subject to the arrangement of Rule IX.; and if no such name appear, then that of any country, province, city, town or place so appearing, to be adopted as the heading.

Articles to be inquired of within an ecclesiastical district to be entered under the name of such district.

XXXV. If no name of any assembly or country, to be preferred as above, appear on the title, the name of the editor, (if there be any,) to be used as a heading; or, if no editor's name appear, that of the translator, if there be one. Reporters to be considered as editors.

XXXVI. Adjectives formed from the name of a person, party, place or denomination, to be treated as the names from which they are formed.

XXXVII. If two names occur seeming to have an equal claim, the first to be chosen.

Reports of civil actions to be catalogued under the

name of that party to the suit which stands first upon the title-page.

In criminal proceedings the name of the defendant to be adopted as a heading.

Trials relating to any vessel to be entered under the name of such vessel.

XXXVIII. In the case of anonymous works, to which none of the foregoing rules can be applied, the first substantive in the title (or if there be no substantive, the first word) to be selected as the heading. A substantive, adjectively used, to be taken in conjunction with its following substantive as forming one word; and the same to be done with respect to adjectives incorporated with their following substantive. The entries which may occur under the same heading to succeed each other in strict alphabetical order.

XXXIX. Whenever the name of the author of an anonymous publication is known to, or conjectured by, the librarian, the same to be inserted at the end of the title, between brackets.

XL. Works without the author's name, and purporting to comment or remark on a work of which the title is set forth in that of such publication, to be catalogued under the same heading as the work remarked or commented upon.

XLI. In the case of pseudonymous publications, the book to be catalogued under the author's feigned name; and his real name, if discovered, to be inserted in brackets, immediately after the feigned name, preceded by the letters *i. e.*

XLII. Assumed names, or names used to designate an office, profession, party, or qualification of the writer, to be treated as real names. Academical names to follow the same rule. The works of an author not assuming any name but describing himself by a circumlocution, to be considered anonymous.

XLIII. Works falsely attributed in their title to a particular person, to be treated as pseudonymous.

XLIV. Works of several writers, collectively published, to be entered according to the following rules, [and the separate pieces of the various authors included in the collection to be separately entered in the order in which they occur; excepting merely collections of letters, charters, short extracts from larger works, and similar compilations.]

That part of the foregoing rule which is inserted between brackets has not been acted upon, in order to accelerate the printing of the catalogue.

XLV. In any series of printed works, which embraces the collected productions of various writers upon particular subjects, such as Ugolini Thesaurus Antiq. Sacrarum, Gronovii Thesaurus Antiq. Græcarum, the work to be entered under the name of the editor.

Works of several authors published together, but not under a collective title, to be catalogued under the name of the first author, notwithstanding an editor's name may appear on the work.

XLVI. If the editor's name do not appear, the whole collection to be entered under the collective title, in the same manner as anonymous works.

In cataloguing collections without an editor's name, and having a collective title, the heading to be taken from such collective title without reference to that portion of the title which may follow.

XLVII. General collections of laws, edicts, ordinances, or other public acts of a similar description, to be entered under the name of the state or nation in

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which or by whom they were sanctioned, signed, or promulgated. Collections extending only to one reign or period of supreme government by one person, as well as detached laws and documents separately enacted and issued, to be catalogued under the name of the person in whose name and by whose authority they are enacted or sanctioned; such names to be entered alphabetically under the principal entry of the state or nation, after the general collections. When more than one name occurs, the first to be preferred.

XLVIII. Collections of laws, edicts, &c., of several countries or nations to be catalogued according to rules XLV. and XLVI.

XLIX. The same to be done with respect to laws on one or more particular subjects, either merely collected or digested in some particular order, or used as text to some particular comment or treatise.

L. The names of translators or commentators to be stated in cataloguing and entering a work, if they occur in the title page; and when they do not occur, but are known to or conjectured by the librarian, to be supplied between brackets.

LI. The works of translators to be entered under the name of the original author. The same rule to be observed with respect to the works of commentators, if the same be accompanied with the text complete.

LII. Translations to be entered immediately after the original, generally with only the indication of the language into which the version has been made, in italics; but if any material alteration in the title have been introduced, so much of the title of the translation to be given as may be deemed requisite, or a short explanation in English added, between brackets.

LIII. Commentaries unaccompanied by the text, to be entered under the commentator's name; if without a name, or with an assumed name, then according to the rules laid down for anonymous or pseudonymous works.

LIV. No work ever to be entered twice at full length. Whenever requisite, cross-references to be introduced.

LV. Cross-references to be divided into three classes, from name to name, from name to work, and from work to work. Those of the first class to contain merely the name, title, or office of the person referred to as entered; those of the second, so much of the title referred to besides, as, together with the size and date, may give the means of at once identifying, under its heading, the book referred to; those of the third class to contain moreover so much of the title referred from, as may be necessary to ascertain the object of the reference.

LVI. Cross-references of the first class to be made in the following instances:

From the titles of noblemen, and from the sees of archbishops or bishops, to the family name, or the first name under which the works of such personages are to be entered according to the foregoing rules.

LVII. From the family name of persons whose works are to be entered under the Christian or first name, to such Christian or first name; excepting in the case of sovereigns, or princes belonging to sovereign houses.

LVIII. From any surnames either spelt, or in any way used, in a manner differing from the form adopted in the principal entry, to such entry.

LIX. From any of the names or surnames used by an author besides that under which the principal entry is made, to the one so preferred.

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LX. From the real to the assumed name of authors; adding *pseud.* to the entry referred to in the cross-reference.

LXI. Cross-references of the second or third class, according to circumstances, to be made in the following instances:

From the names of editors, or of biographers who have prefixed an author's life to his works, (provided such names appear in the book,) to the principal entry.

LXII. From the names of authors of anonymous or pseudonymous works supplied in the title, as well as from the names of authors who have shared with another in writing a work, or have continued it, and also from the names of translators, commentators, or annotators, either appearing on the title, or supplied as above directed, to the main entry.

LXIII. From the name of any person the subject of any biography or narrative, to its author; stating briefly, in italics, after the name referred from, the peculiar designation of the biography in the work referred to; or, if this cannot be done, using the nearest English word, in brackets and italics, that may give an idea of the object of the cross reference.

In this description of cross-reference the first words of the title of the work referred to to be given, but not its date or size, so that the cross-reference may serve equally for all editions.

LXIV. From any name which may be reasonably conceived to have an equal claim to that selected for the principal entry, to such entry.

LXV. From any author, any whole work of whom or any considerable part of it may be the subject of a commentary, or notes, to the name of the commentator or annotator. No notice to be taken of the name of authors, fragments or inconsiderable parts of whose works are observed upon by the commentator or annotator.

LXVI. From any author whose works, or considerable part of them contained in a collection, are considered so important as to be distinctly specified in the entry of the collection itself, to the principal entry; the volume, or part of the collection in which the article so referred to is found, to be specified.

LXVII. From the names of authors whose entire works or any considerable part of them are included among the collected works of a polygraphic writer, or translator, to the principal entry.

LXVIII. From the name of a state or nation to which a collection of laws, entered under any other heading, belongs, to the main entry.

From the name of the superior of any ecclesiastical district who promulgates articles for inquiry to the name of such district.

From the name of any party to a civil action to the principal entry.

LXIX. Entries to be made in the following order: Cross-references to be placed at the beginning of the entry, from which they are made, in the alphabetical order of the entries referred to.

LXX. Collections of all the works of an author in their original language only, to be entered immediately after the cross-references; the editions without date, and those of which the date cannot be ascertained even by approximation, to precede all those bearing date, or of which the date can be supplied either positively or by approximation. The latter to follow according to their date, whether apparent in any part of the book, or supplied. Editions by the same editor, or such as are expressly stated to follow a specific text or edition, and

editions with the same notes or commentary, to succeed each other immediately in their chronological order after the entry of that which is, or is considered to be, the earliest.

LXXI. The text of the collected works, accompanied by a translation, to follow those having the text only, and in the same order.

LXXII. The translations of such collected works into the Latin language only to precede those in any other language in the above order; the Latin translations to be followed by those in English. Translations in any other language to follow according to the alphabetical order of the name of the language in English. If the volume contain two or more translations, without the text, the entry to be made according to the alphabetical order of the first of the languages employed. Translations into the same language, and their several editions, to be entered in conformity with the rules laid down for the entries of the originals.

LXXIII. Collections of two or more works of an author to be entered in the order and according to the rules laid down for the collections of all the works of a writer, after the translations of the whole works; such partial collections to precede, as are known or are supposed to contain the largest number of an author's works.

LXXIV. Selections, or collected fragments, from the works of an author, to follow the partial collections of his works, and to be entered according to the above rules.

LXXV. Separate works of an author to succeed each other alphabetically; the several editions and translations of each of them to be entered in the same manner as directed for the collected works of a writer.

LXXVI. Entire portions of a separate work to succeed the work from which they are taken, in the order above directed. If the whole work to which they belong do not occur, such portions to be entered after all the separate works, but according to the principles laid down for the latter.

LXXVII. Works not written by the person under whose name they are to be catalogued according to the foregoing rules, to be entered alphabetically as an appendix, and in chronological succession, when more than one article occurs in the same alphabetical series, after all the works of the person whose name is selected, if any occur in the catalogue. Volumes without date, or the date of which cannot be supplied, to be entered first.

LXXVIII. The same rule as to the alphabetical and chronological arrangement to apply to works entered under any other heading than the name of a person.

LXXIX. The Old and New Testament and their parts, to be catalogued under the general head "Bible," and arranged in the following order:—

1st. The Old and New Testaments in the original Hebrew and Greek only, chronologically arranged.

2d. The same, in polyglot editions, which include the original texts; beginning with those editions which contain most translations.

3d. The same, translated into other languages, but without the original; those editions to precede which contain most languages; then translations into one language only, arranged as directed in rule LXXII.

4th. Editions, with comments, to follow those having the text only, in the same order and according to the same principles. Bibles accompanied by the same comment to follow each other immediately in chronological succession.

5th. The Old Testament only to be next entered, according to the same principles and rules.

6th. Detached parts of the Old Testament then to follow, in the same order in which they are arranged in the English authorised version of the Scriptures, and to be entered as directed for the whole Bible.

7th. The Apocrypha, as declared by the Church of England, to be next catalogued and entered according to the same rules.

8th. The New Testament to be next catalogued, and then its parts, according to the foregoing rules.

9th. General cross-references to be made from the several names of the inspired writers, as well as from the names of the several parts of Scripture, to the general head "Bible." Particular cross-references to be made from the names of editors, commentators, translators, &c., to the precise entry under which the part of Holy writ referred from in the cross-reference occurs.

10th. The names of parts of the Bible, as well as of inspired writers, to be expressed in the form adopted in the authorised English version of the Scriptures.

LXXX. All acts, memoirs, transactions, journals, minutes, &c., of academies, institutes, associations, universities, or societies learned, scientific, or literary, by whatever name known or designated, as well as works by various hands, forming part of a series of volumes edited by any such society, to be catalogued under the general name "Academies" and alphabetically entered, according to the English name of the country and town at which the sittings of the society are held, in the following order. The primary division to be of the four parts of the world in alphabetical succession, Australia and Polynesia being considered as appendixes to Asia; the first subdivision to be of the various empires, kingdoms, or other independent governments into which any part of the world is divided, in alphabetical order; and a second subdivision of each state to follow, according to the various cities or towns, alphabetically disposed, belonging to each state, in which any society of this description meets. The acts, &c., of each society, when more than one meet at the same place, to be entered according to the name under which the society published its first work, in alphabetical series; and the acts, memoirs, &c. of each society to be entered chronologically. Continuations to follow the original entry.

LXXXI. The same rule and arrangement to be followed for "Periodical Publications," which are to be catalogued under this general head, embracing reviews, magazines, newspapers, journals, gazettes, annuals, and all works of a similar nature, in whatever language and under whatever denomination they may be published. The several entries under the last subdivision to be made in alphabetical order according to the first substantive occurring in the title.

LXXXII. All almanacs, calendars, ephemerides of whatever description they be, as well as their companions, appendixes, &c., to be entered under the general head "Ephemerides." The several works under this head to be entered alphabetically according to the first substantive occurring in the title.

LXXXIII. There shall be cross-references from the name of any author, editor, or contributor to any of the above works, appearing in any of the title-pages of any of the volumes, as well as from the peculiar name or designation of any of the societies, from the place at which they hold their meetings, from any place forming part of the peculiar name of a journal, almanac, calendar, &c., from the name under which such publications are generally known, to the main entries of such works.

LXXXIV. Religious and military orders to be designated by the English name under which they are generally known, and entries to be made accordingly.

LXXXV. Anonymous catalogues, whether bearing the title catalogue or any other intended to convey the same meaning, to be entered under the head "Catalogues," subdivided as follows:—1st. Catalogues of public establishments (including those of societies, although not strictly speaking *public*). 2d. Catalogues of private collections, drawn up either for sale or otherwise. 3d. Catalogues of collections not for sale, the possessors of which are not known. 4th. General as well as special catalogues of objects, without any reference to their possessor. 5th. Dealers' catalogues. 6th. Sale catalogues not included in any of the preceding sections.

LXXXVI. Catalogues of the first subdivision to be entered under the name of the place at which the collection exists, as directed for Academies: those of the second, under the name of the collector or possessor: those of the third, in strict alphabetical order, according to the first substantive of the title: those of the fourth, to follow the same rule: those of the fifth, under the dealer's name: those of the sixth, strictly chronologically, supplying the year in brackets whenever omitted, but known to, or conjectured by, the librarian; and when it is impossible to ascertain the precise day and month, for catalogues coming under the same year, in strict alphabetical order before those having a precise date. Catalogues without any date, and the date of which cannot be supplied, to be entered at the beginning of this subdivision in strict alphabetical order, as just directed. With respect to mere dealers' and sale catalogues compiled since the beginning of the present century, such only to be catalogued and entered as may be considered of peculiar interest.

LXXXVII. Cross-references of the second class to be made from the name of the compiler of a catalogue (when supplied by the librarian, and other than the collector or possessor of a collection, a dealer or an auctioneer) to the principal entry.

LXXXVIII. Anonymous Dictionaries of any description, including Lexicons and Vocabularies, to be catalogued under the general head "Dictionaries," and entered in strict alphabetical order according to the first substantive in the title, with cross-references from the author's name, when supplied.

LXXXIX. The same rule to be applied to Encyclopædias, the name of the editor of which does not appear on the title, and which shall be catalogued under the general head "Encyclopædias," with a cross-reference from the editor's name, when supplied in the principal entry, to such entry.

XC. Missals, Breviaries, Offices, Horæ, Prayer Books, Liturgies, and works of the same description (not compiled by private individuals and in their individual capacity, in which case they are to be catalogued and entered according to the general rules laid down for other works,) to be entered under the general head "Liturgies," in one strict alphabetical series, according to the English denomination of the communion, sect, or religious order for whom they are specially intended; if drawn up for any particular church, congregation, or place of worship, then according to the English name peculiar to such church, congregation, or place of worship; if any work of this description occur not coming under either of these two classes, then the first substantive in the title to be preferred as a heading. Entries under the same heading to be made in strict alphabetical order.

XCI. Cross-references of the second class to be made from the peculiar name or designation of any of the churches, communions, sects, religious orders, or places of worship, as well as from the name under which any of the works mentioned in the preceding article is generally known, to the main entry.